

Mini Review

The Effects on Humanity of the Ignored Pandemic of Child Sexual Abuse: Homosexuality, Psychopathy, Serial Killers, Psychosis-Schizophrenia, Drug Addictions, Eating Disorders and Many other Consequences Such as Dictators: Actualized

Alejandro Cuevas-Sosa*

Centro de Prevención y Tratamiento de la Violencia Sexual e Intrafamiliar, México

Abstract

I propose the examination of imprinting resulting from sexual abuse as a potential factor that may influence various outcomes, including homosexuality, stuttering, autism in both men and women, serial killer and paraphilias (fetichism, exhibitionism, pedophilia, voyeurism and other examples). It is suggested that imprinting originally triggered by sexual abuse might contribute to the development of these conditions. One possible sequence, among others, could involve the following: Sexual abuse imprinting (leading to imprinting of homosexuality) may be associated with imprinting of stuttering and autism in both men and women. These conditions, observed with an average ratio of four men to one woman. Also, sexual killer behavior and paraphilias use to be related to child sexual abuse. All these effects are known to be quite challenging to modify. These collective observations give rise to the imprinting syndrome of sexual abuse.

*Corresponding author: Alejandro Cuevas-Sosa, Centro de Prevención y Tratamiento de la Violencia Sexual e Intrafamiliar, México, E-mail: commentstoneuno@gmail.com

Citation: Cuevas-Sosa A (2025) The Effects on Humanity of the Ignored Pandemic of Child Sexual Abuse: Homosexuality, Psychopathy, Serial Killers, Psychosis-Schizophrenia, Drug Addictions, Eating Disorders and Many other Consequences Such as Dictators: Actualized. HSOA J Altern Complement Integr Med 11: 567.

Received: March 17, 2025; **Accepted:** March 25, 2025; **Published:** March 31, 2025

Copyright: © 2025 Cuevas-Sosa A. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Through bioenergemal communication, we establish interaction with human BEGs that arrive at the BEL universe after people bio-collapse (die). This BEL information does not intend to ratify or rectify the official version of these facts; it only presents the bioinformation that some BEGs shared with us. All invited BEGs agreed that their names and comments could be published.

Keywords: Autism; Biointerfaceme; Bioenerscience; Biomatter; Bioenergeme; Biocommunication; Biomaterial-biointerfacemal-bioenergemal Universes; Bioenergemal Communication; Chemical Submission; Dictators; Drug Addictions; Eating Disorders; Homosexuality; Imprinting; Intuiscience; Intuilish; Neuromindego; Paraphilias; Pope Francis; Psychopathy; Psychosis-Schizophrenia; Religious figures; Stuttering; Serial Killers; Sexual Abuse; Tourette Syndrome

Abbreviations

BML: Biomaterial

BEL: Bioenergemal

BEG: Bioenergeme

BIFL: Biointerfacemal

BELC: Bioenergemal Communication

BIOCOM: Biocommunication

NMEGO: Neuromindego

UU: Unit Universe

Ints: Intuitions

Introduction

I propose the examination of imprinting resulting from sexual abuse as a potential factor that may influence various outcomes, including homosexuality, stuttering, and autism in both men and women, serial murder syndrome and paraphilias (fetichism, exhibitionism, pedophilia, voyeurism and other examples) [Ints 01/24 & 03/10/2025]. It is suggested that imprinting originally triggered by sexual abuse might contribute to the development of these conditions. One possible sequence, among others, could involve the following: Sexual abuse imprinting (leading to imprinting of homosexuality) may be associated with imprinting of stuttering and autism in both men and women. These conditions, observed with an average ratio of four men to one woman, are known to be challenging to modify. These collective observations give rise to the imprinting syndrome of sexual abuse, serial murder syndrome and paraphilias (fetichism, exhibitionism, pedophilia, voyeurism and other examples) [Ints 01/24 & 03/10/2025].

Imprinting Syndrome of Sexual Abuse

Imprinting refers to an early stage in an animal's life, or a sensitive stage when it forms bonds and develops its own identity. Through sexual imprinting, young animals learn mate preferences at an early

age by observing and learning to imitate their parents as role models, as is the case with humans and various other animal species. Natural sexual imprinting prevents consanguinity or mating with relatives, and avoids inbreeding or mating between close members of a community.

Summary of Surveys

A summary of surveys conducted in 2016 in several countries on heterosexuality and homosexuality in men and women concluded that, on average, 2% of men and 0.5% of women identify as exclusively homosexual, resulting in a ratio of 4:1 for men and women. Additionally, 0.5% of men and 0.5% of women identify as predominantly homosexual, 0.5% of men and 1% of women as bisexual, 4% of men and 10% of women as mostly heterosexual, and 93% of men and 88% of women recognized themselves as exclusively heterosexual [1]. This reflects the fact that 7% of men and 12% of women show variations in their sexual preferences. Homosexual variants occur in both sexes, and if preferred, they cannot easily modify a certain sexual preference. In a 1997 survey in the United States, 46% of gay or bisexual individuals had a history of childhood sexual abuse, whereas only 12% did not. This study affirms: "Given these findings, it appears that being sexually abused as a child may affect the propensity of adult men to fantasize about young men [2,3]."

Definition of Child Sexual Abuse

Sexual abuse is defined as any sexual activity involving a child who does not provide or cannot provide consent. It can be forced sexual contact or through threats, regardless of the age of those who participate, as well as any sexual contact between an adult (or an older boy or girl), either through deception or if the minor, boy or girl, understands the sexual nature of that activity. Under overcrowded conditions, instances of homosexual rape have been reported to occur with greater frequency, such as in boarding schools and prisons [4,5].

Children Early Development

In children, sexual abuse can result in specific attachments and well-defined aversion. In addition, these children may perceive their sexual inclinations differently due to the absence of a consolidated heterosexual gender imprinting identity, which they may be unaware of and consider foreign to them [6]. This perception may result from aversive imprinting caused by the sexual abuse experience. Consequently, individuals may perceive their bodies as incongruent with their sexual preferences, leading to rejection of their own physicality. Such perceptions can persist into adolescence, adulthood, and old age, with individuals perceiving their homosexual orientation as unchangeable and normal. When the imprinting of the minor's gender identity was preserved and coexisted with the imprinting resulting from sexual abuse, such as instances of short duration or lower intensity (e.g., when it was a woman who groped the child's anus), then the assaulted person could present both heterosexual and homosexual impulses or bisexuality. Some young homosexuals may conceal their sexual preferences, even resorting to extreme measures like suicide if they fear exposure. Homosexuality in adults may often be accompanied by aggressive sexual impulses and harm to babies [7]. Homosexuality may attenuate or nullify reproduction, too [8].

Certain brain areas may be involved, including the inner face of the temporal lobes and a part of the limbic system. This system is a part of the brain involved in behavioral and emotional responses, especially when it comes to behaviors that we need to survive, such as feeding, reproducing, caring for our offspring, and fighting or flight responses. Additionally, the emotional register of experiences directs human existence involuntarily [9,10].

Political not Medical Decisions on Homosexuality

Some people, both men and women, often ask for a sufficient-ly clear and consistent explanation of the causes of homosexuality. However, the search was halted when in 1973 the American Psychiatric Association removed homosexuality from its list of mental disorders. Ronald Bayer, author of what is considered the most explicit account of the 1973 decision, described what actually happened: "A furious egalitarianism that challenged every instance of authority had compelled psychiatric experts to negotiate the pathological status of homosexuality with homosexuals themselves. The result was not a conclusion based on an approximation of the scientific truth as dictated by reason, but was instead an action demanded by the ideological temper of the times [11]." They tried to normalize homosexuality and all they got was to normalize child sexual abuse, thereby leading to the affectation of any form of family nucleus.

Dubious Benefits of Therapies

Of course, there have always been psychotherapeutic approaches to homosexuality, from the psychoanalytic approach (which tries to help the person to make conscious the presumed unconscious causes), group psychotherapy (seeks improved general adjustment), to eclectic approaches like the Rational Emotive Therapy, or just psychotherapy; and, currently, from the criticized reconversion therapies (they seek to make the homosexual become heterosexual) to those that invite homosexuality to be seen only as a lifestyle choice. All these psychotherapeutic approaches claim to be effective depending on the person in question [12].

Acquired Stuttering

The imprinting of early sexual abuse may coincide with other sensitive stages of development, such as language learning [13]. It can interfere with language acquisition and impede the learning and expression of language. This interference can lead to acquired stuttering, which manifests as a result of panic and distress caused by the abuse [14]. Therefore, I propose that sexual abuse may not only impact sexual preferences in men and women but also affect language learning and expression. Thus, stuttering, as a consequence of imprinting difficulties, becomes challenging to overcome [15]. On average, this condition affects four adult males for every female (4:1 ratio) [16]. This may reflect altered filial (familial) imprinting because the children learn language primarily from their parents [17]. Limbic imprinting can persist because of the many fears and humiliations faced by these individuals [18]. Some medications that antagonize the neurotransmitter dopamine are effective in reducing the severity of stuttering symptoms.

Stuttering and Autism

Autism is a neurodevelopmental disorder that arises during the first two years of life and persists for the rest of life. It is characterized by a wide variety of communication disorders, including restricted motor skills, limited social interaction, distractibility, impulsiveness, passivity, learning difficulties, and self-absorption as defeated. Autism traits are so varied that specialists speak of autism spectrum disorder. There is no cure for autism, and support consists of helping individuals acquire habits that allow them to adapt to their limitations or peculiarities, even with the help of medications. The typical frequency of autism in men and women is 4:1 or 3:1, respectively [19]. Simultaneous presentation of stuttering and autism has also been

reported, as has sexual abuse in children with autism. Imprinting forms the biological basis that researchers statistically detect when studying homosexuality, acquired stuttering, and autism.

Tourette Syndrome

Tourette's Syndrome may be another more serious complication of childhood sexual abuse, which shares very similar symptoms with stuttering and autism, and also follows a 4:1 ratio for males and females. They occasionally behave in a sexopathic and or sociopathic way [20-22]. In Tourette's Syndrome, the imprinting of repeated sexual abuse can completely disorganize the personality. Without a doubt, child sexual abuse must be typified as one of the most serious crimes. If the exponential increase in the sexual abuse of children continues, the Western culture will end up destroying itself, just like those other cultures or institutions (religious, military, wild communities) that maintain this same practice.

Gender abuse is also relevant, and with results similar to sexual abuse, when, for example, the father and or the mother reject their baby because it is a girl or a boy. A similar response of rejection can be presented with stepchildren and even with adopted sons or daughters. In all these cases, parents or guardians usually respond with an impulsive aversive imprinting not only towards the sex of the babies but also against their existence.

This is how the relentless, stealthy, and hard-to-modify imprinting syndrome of child sexual abuse is integrated. It is important to acknowledge that the determination of truth and falsehood can sometimes be influenced by dominant societal groups, prioritizing subjective biases over research findings and consistent statistical data. Therefore, it is advisable to consider contrasting approaches and perspectives in the examination of these complex topics. The harmful concealment of the deceptive sexual culture in the West made an industry is evident [23,24].

Eating Disorders

BELC 08/26/2024. We are inviting 10 men and 10 women diagnosed with eating disorders such as bulimia and anorexia nervosa to participate in the BEG. *How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood? Raise your hand. Men: "Six". Women: "Eight". Men, how was your NMEGO affected?* "It was different, doctor, for each of us, but in general it made us feel that our body was unpleasant, our person was inadequate, that we had to be very clean or very... giving an image that according to us did not correspond to reality or that we had to deceive and our mood was affected by making it variable... Well, we are... we want to please, but at the same time we hurt a lot and even though we don't want to, we hurt ourselves... We also feel that it is easy for us to be hurt, rejected, devalued and suddenly we feel very overrated... Fear and guilt limit us, but sometimes we cannot limit ourselves to food... Our being becomes disorganized and that is how we live..." *Women, how was your NMEGO affected?* "Well, sometimes we feel like our existence is worthless, that no matter what we do, we are no longer whole. Sometimes we are our allies, but sometimes we are our enemies, and we constantly attack each other without being able to stop for a moment of peace. Sometimes, it's a family that becomes a family of sexual abuse, and that separates everyone, individualizes them, and they can no longer integrate but attack, sometimes with carelessness, apathy, or disorganization. These are ways we learn to treat each other. This means that sometimes we lie, or other times we are the most frank and sincere people, but fear scares us, and we once again create a shell and compensate through food or other addictions or obsessions... We get tangled up and don't know how to untangle it; it's a problem."

Suicidal

BELC 08/26/2024. We invited the BEG of 20 men and 20 women who have committed suicide. *How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood? Raise your hand? Men: "Twelve". Women: "Fifteen". Men, was the sexual abuse that disastrous and intolerable for your NMEGO?* "Doctor, that's true, and even if it was just touching, there are those of us who experience it as an irreparable problem that torments us every night and sometimes even every day." *Alfredo Torres Larios*, a suicide researcher, feels spontaneously included in this group. *Women, was the sexual abuse that disastrous and intolerable for your NMEGO?* "Yes, doctor, because the vulnerable age you are at can be a factor for someone to attack you, underestimate you, and threaten you. They all want to be different, but end up looking and feeling different; even their own appearance is neglected to the point that it no longer matters, and it increasingly ceases to matter. Some agree sometimes, but we want to disappear through thinness, while others want to alienate others through obesity or some grotesque behavior. Some imitate us, but don't know why we are that way." *Alfonsina Storni*: "Doctor, regardless of whether a person who has suffered sexual abuse succeeds, it doesn't negate the imprint of sexual abuse. I applaud your tireless work in raising awareness against sexual abuse and its normalization and indifference. The same thing happens to men and women, Doctor."

Effects on Humanity of Child Sexual Abuse

I insist that the global pandemic of sexual abuse of infants, girls, and boys, and the devastating effect its aftermath has had on the family, on men, on women, and on humanity as a whole, will reach its growth limit of 10 billion inhabitants by the end of this 21st century, and in the 22nd and 23rd centuries will begin to decline as rapidly as its increase, reaching a limit of approximately 2 billion inhabitants in just 10 generations [25]. Not to mention that if one or more wars involving atomic bombs were to occur, the outlook for humanity's survival would change drastically (they claim that in 1986 there were 70,300 active atomic bombs, and that by 2024 there will be 12,121 atomic bombs in the world [26]). In reality, it is not known, or they do not want to reveal, how many of these atomic weapons exist. They treat humanity as if it were made up of minors). Be careful of dictators...

Sociopaths-Psychopaths-Serial Killers Syndrome

BELC 08/26/2024. We are inviting to the BEG of 10 men and 10 women diagnosed as psychopaths. *How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood? Raise your hand. Men: "Ten". Women: "Ten". Men, how was your NMEGO affected?* "We all experienced some form of sexual abuse, and we had to face the need to alter our behavior in a way that allowed us to confront or go against someone or something that violated our personality." *How severe is this diagnosis?* "Just as severe as sexual abuse, the abuse is repeated, and that's why it's common to find NMEGO alterations in us. The experience isn't shared, and a fantasy is created that we ourselves distort about our existence." *Women, how was your NMEGO affected?* "Equally, 10 of them raised their hands, and they all said the same thing, saying that they had all experienced some form of sexual abuse. They confirm what the men said, although the forms of aggression vary, as do the types of victims sought. The origin is the same condition. And we also distort the situation because it will only be a form of pointing fingers, but not of understanding, given how grotesque the experience is. It is better to disconnect from our own existence than to live trying to correct it." *Correcting what can no longer be corrected...* "Exactly, how can we correct that experience if we are convinced that we are going to be eliminated, attacked, and even worse, discredited? We

know that our fear is so great that we end up in the same circumstance.”

BELC 09/01/2024, includes four sections. **1)** We invite Madame Curie, Abdus Salam, and Esther to accompany us throughout the bio-communication. *We invite the BEG of 20 men and 20 women who have behaved, whether discovered or not, as serial killers. How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood? Raise your hand? Men: “Twelve”. Women: “Nine”. Men, was the abuse excessively cruel?* “Yes, doctor, that’s how we lived it, and that’s why we don’t like to remember those difficult moments or intuit now about it.” *How did your NMEGO lead you to commit serial homicides?* “First, doctor, it feels as if we’re being seduced by a specific person from the outside, and we feel trapped by that person. Then we feel a sense of distrust and detachment. Then a very strong struggle begins between desire and passion and the base instincts of our sexuality, and this makes us feel terrible because we unleash all our resentment and fury, and that’s when we begin to devise a way to attack the other person. We don’t know how, and we lose ourselves, and it’s an unchangeable objective.” *Mainly women?* “Yes, doctor, mainly.” *Men too?* “We see men as allies, but also as enemies when they are allies of women. However, it isn’t always the case. There’s a lot of dualities in what we think, in what we conceive.” *Did you ever feel envy of some men?* “Yes, doctor, sometimes terrifying and, at other times, lustful, because they can achieve what we want, they can achieve their goal.” *Did you eat body parts of your victims?* “Some of us did, but not all, but we did like having him/her around. Seeing what he/she had become.” *What part of the body attracted you the most?* “There isn’t one in particular; we like to feel like we can control it. But, at the same time, we realize now that we are the ones who are controlled.” *How did your mother’s or father’s partner participate in this sexual abuse as children?* “It varies greatly because sometimes they are accomplices; they are the trash that takes the memories. Likewise, they don’t usually have that much... they tend to be selfish and distant.” *Was there any financial arrangement by your father or mother for them to sexually abuse you?* “Yes, doctor, sometimes yes, and other times we realized about their illness, which was transmitted to us. They harmed their child for money or for pleasure.” *Were you children of an unwanted pregnancy by your parents?* “Yes, doctor, we were children almost at the point of biocollapse” [death]. *How many of you grew up with only your mother?* “Six”. *How many of you grew up with only your father?* “Two”. *Two with both parents. Were you frequently threatened as children that you would be murdered?* “Yes, doctor, we also experienced that from the womb, we lived it like that.” *Did you live in a prison as a child?* “Some of us did, but some of us lived like in a prison, and so we preferred the streets. Some of us lived there in the prison, and others, our mother later left [the prison]. Sometimes we preferred her to be locked up.” *Did you choose your victims, or was it completely by chance?* “It’s an attraction on both sides; at first, it’s by chance, and then we observe them; however, we’ve already chosen them. And we just need to get to know them to seduce them. And make them our allies.” *What did you feel when you murdered someone?* “Well, at first, a lot of fear, a lot of anger. It’s a very strong impulse that lasts until it’s carried out. Then comes a feeling of tranquility, somewhere between victory and enjoyment. But it’s also replaced later by a feeling of emptiness.” *Did you dedicate the crime to someone?* “It’s up to each person, depending on what each person is looking for, what each person has experienced. For example, if someone experienced it as an offering, as a gift, then they surely did it because they owed that debt. They didn’t do it for themselves, but for someone else. When

you don’t want to feel that deep emptiness, that’s when a third party gets involved and you can’t take it anymore, so you cover it up that way. The cases vary.” *Did you cause the authorities to discover you?* “Yes, doctor, there comes a time when our NMEGO can no longer plan, flee, or try to escape from itself.” *What do you say about childhood sexual abuse?* “Doctor, no one deserves to be treated with any type of abuse, much less sexual abuse. When sexual abuse occurs, it’s because other abuse has already taken place, and if not, it’s about to take place. In other words, it doesn’t happen alone... it leaves very deep wounds and the traits become more diverse, but it’s very difficult.” *How does your BEG feel?* “Currently, we feel like we’ve lived in that void we always wanted to escape, but the NMEGO deceived us because it was only temporary play. The NMEGO helps with that because [when biocollapsed], you lose it and that’s it, but you can’t escape from the BEG, but it’s empty.” *Would you like to add anything else?* “Thank you, doctor, for asking us this. It’s like filling the BEG with something different, we don’t know what it is, but it’s different.”

Women, was the abuse excessively cruel? “All abuse, even if not excessive, is cruel. Some of us experienced it as more intense or cruel, and others experienced it very cruel, but we didn’t experience it that way. We all experienced it as cruel, senseless.” *How did your NMEGO lead you to commit serial homicides?* “Doctor, something inside us, our NMEGO, took hold of us without stopping us from achieving a goal. Faced with the difficulty of getting rid of that force, we let ourselves be carried away by the moment until we culminated in the murder and then another. It seemed like we didn’t need that force, but it becomes a condition, a personal motive.” *As revenge?* “Yes, as revenge or betrayal, yes, that’s how we experienced it, as revenge or betrayal.” *The more vulnerable the person, the more this murderous tendency emerged?* “Yes, doctor, because the more vulnerable the person, the more anger, resentment, and difficulty in stopping it could arise.” *Perhaps you were reliving your own vulnerability from when you were abused as children?* “Doctor, we hadn’t seen it that way, but we certainly experienced that vulnerability, albeit in an inappropriate way.” *Mainly men? Mainly women? Or both, women and men?* “Well, it didn’t make any difference. Although there were mostly men, but women were also present.” *Did you eat body parts of your victims?* “Doctor, sometimes yes, with that feeling of resentment, hatred, revenge, there was that need, in other cases it only materialized in murder and the hiding of the body.” *How did your mother’s or father’s partner participate in this sexual abuse when you were young?* “In some cases, they do seem to have participated and been involved, yes, doctor, because those who were negligent participated by doing nothing; they didn’t prevent what was happening.” *Was there some financial arrangement by your father or mother for you to be sexually abused?* “Certainly yes, it’s very common. If there wasn’t money, there was some merchandise, there was something in return, yes, they received it. Sometimes these people don’t have resources either, but they steal it somehow.” *Were you the children of an unwanted pregnancy by your parents?* “Of course, Doctor, we were never wanted.” *How many of you only knew your mother?* “Twenty.” *Were you frequently threatened with murder as children?* “Yes, doctor, some of us were even threatened with being expelled from our mother’s womb.” *Did you live in prison as a child?* “No, doctor, it was free time. Although we committed murders, some managed to evade that authority somehow.” *Did you choose your victims, or was it completely by chance?* “Of course we chose them; we followed our own ideas and were clear about who we were looking for.” *Mainly men?* “Mainly, but women too.” *What did you feel when you*

murdered someone? “Satisfaction, from the moment you undertook that goal, letting yourself be driven by that desire.” *Did you feel strong?* “Yes, doctor, we felt strong, very motivated.” *Did you encourage the authorities to discover you?* “After several murders, we felt we were going to be an example, a demonstration that what we were doing was just.” *Do you want to add anything else?* “Nothing else, doctor.”

Psychosis-Schizophrenia

BELC 06/22/2021. Using the Innovative BEL Instrument (IBI), 100 random men from the *current era* were shown on the screen; *What percentage of them were raped in childhood, adolescence, and/or as adults?* “70%.” One hundred random men from the Middle Ages: *What percentage were raped?* “80%.” One hundred random men from the 5th and 4th centuries before our era (boe; Homer, Heracles, Socrates): *What percentage were raped?* “70%.”

Using the IBI, 100 random women from the *current era* were shown on the screen; *What percentage of them were raped in childhood, adolescence, and/or as adults?* “80%.” One hundred random women from the Middle Ages: *What percentage were raped?* “80%.” One hundred random women from the 5th and 4th centuries boe: *What percentage were raped?* “80%.”

Using the IBI, out of 50 men and 50 women diagnosed with *schizophrenia*, *how many were raped before developing schizophrenia?* Men: “50% (25).” Women: “60% (30).”

Using the IBI, out of 50 men and 50 women diagnosed with *psychosis*, *how many were raped before developing psychosis?* Men: “60% (30).” Women: “60% (30).”

Humanity is irreparably poisoned by child sexual abuse and its consequences [Ints 03/18/2025].

Members of the Military

2) We invite the BEG of 15 men and 15 women who have served in the military since they were recruits and privates. *How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood?* Raise your hand. Men: “Eight.” Women: “Ten.” Men, *how was your NMEGO affected?* “Doctor, of course, sexual abuse is an event that you carry with you, but sometimes the NMEGO doesn’t remember it, but it will manifest at some point.” Women, *how was your NMEGO affected?* “Doctor, the NMEGO is affected by sexual abuse, even if you forget it or don’t remember it.”

How many of you suffered sexual abuse by members of the military? Please raise your hand? Men: “Six.” Women: “Ten.” Men, *how was your NMEGO affected by abuse in the military?* “Doctor, after we’ve suffered abuse from a partner, as the level increases, it can become more intense, for example, penetration. That’s why we make it seem consensual and then move on to more. So, we live with the ideal of staying there. At that moment, the ideal is the pursuit of that power.” *What argument did sexual abusers use to abuse you?* “Sometimes, yes. With that, they could break any rule and do whatever they wanted.” *Did you become sexual abusers afterward?* “Four of us did, some didn’t have those ideas in their NMEGO.” Women, *how was your NMEGO affected by the abuse in the military?* “Doctor, it affected you in different areas, mainly emotionally, but we never inclined to leave the military.” *Why?* “Because of our parents’ ideals, having a sense of defense, of power.” *What argument did the sexual abusers*

use to abuse you? “Yes, doctor, always, that [the higher hierarchy] was the argument and the rest of us had to obey.” *Did women also abuse you?* “Yes, some did. The roughest ones sought out their victims and, in that way, managed to make the others submit, whatever their intentions.” *Did you become abusers afterward?* “Five of us did, it was inappropriate because we ourselves opposed it; it was just a whim, partly out of revenge, but we felt it was justice, and that’s how it should have been.”

Drug Addicts

3) We invite the BEG of 15 men and 15 women who have been addicted to illicit drugs of all kinds (marijuana, cocaine, morphine, fentanyl, and whatever). *How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood? Raise your hand? Men:* “Ten”. *Women:* “Ten”. Men, *how was your NMEGO affected?* “Doctor, it inevitably transformed.” *Do you mean it became useless?* “Yes, doctor, it practically became insensitive, there was no longer any contact with reality, it was like living like an automaton.” Women, *how was your NMEGO affected?* “Doctor, there really is no difference. It also affected us completely; our NMEGO no longer functioned properly.”

Alcoholics

4) We invite the BEG of 15 men and 15 women who have been alcoholics. *How many of you suffered sexual abuse in childhood? Raise your hand? Men:* “Eleven”. *Women:* “Eleven”. Men, *how was your NMEGO affected?* “Doctor, we lived in situations in which we lost our sense of reality, even our sense of existence; our projects collapsed.” Women, *how was your NMEGO affected?* “Yes, doctor. We radically abandoned what we, as human beings, women, mothers, should have done. Our existence is transformed.”

Caroline Darian

In her book, *And I Stopped Calling You Dad*, Caroline Darian recounts the sexual abuse that her mother and other women suffered for years. Dominique, her father, prepared a cocktail of anti-anxiety drugs (benzodiazepines), tranquilizers (Lorazepam), and others with sedative side effects, which is what GHB (gamma hydroxybutyrate) or “liquid ecstasy,” known as the date-rape drug, works like. The abuser mixed this cocktail with wine and gave it to his wife to drink. He put her to sleep for hours, took photos and videos of her, and uploaded them to a website with vulgar captions, inviting his followers to come to his house and rape his wife while she slept, with the sole condition that he take photos and videos and charge them nothing. His mistake was taking upskirt photos of three women in a supermarket who had sued him. When the agents began investigating, they discovered the entire abusive and perverse plot this man had been carrying out in France since 2011. Although less frequently, he did something similar with his only daughter, Caroline, with his two daughters-in-law, and with other women, usually the wives of the rapists who had been invited. More than 50 rapists were arrested and convicted, ranging from young adults to the elderly.

In her book, Caroline Darian comments: “Chemical submission in the family and social sphere is much more widespread than we think. This modus operandi is the preferred weapon of sexual predators. For the moment, we still lack reliable statistical data to prove it. Needless to say, in 2020, when my father was arrested, no one was talking about it!”

“Difficult to pinpoint, still poorly identified, insufficiently quantified, poorly diagnosed, and therefore with little institutional support, it affects a wide range of people, from women and sometimes men to children, even babies and the elderly, from all social strata. We know about GHB, ..., but who could imagine that someone close to them could chemically abuse them, with drugs from the family medicine cabinet?”

“From femicide to incest, the scandals of recent years show that cases of sexual violence often involve power dynamics that transform isolated incidents into systematic practices. Unfortunately, *chemical submission* is no exception: most victims are women, and nearly 70% of reported cases involve sexual assault. The private sphere is the first to be implicated in this type of violence [27].”

Pope Francis

“...it is enough for even one case of abuse to come to light in the Church for it to become a monstrosity in itself. With shame and repentance, the Church must ask forgiveness for the terrible harm these consecrated persons have committed by sexually abusing children, a crime that generates deep wounds of pain and helplessness, first and foremost in the victims, but also in their families and in the community... No silence or concealment on this issue can be tolerated, neither outside the Church nor even within it. It is not a negotiable issue.”

“These types of situations must always be taken very, very seriously, without hesitation or underestimation.”

“The pain of the victims is a complaint that... has always been ignored, hidden, and silenced.”

“This type of crime cannot be subject to a statute of limitations... Undoubtedly, those primarily responsible are those who commit the abuse, but if a bishop knows and does not act, he also becomes responsible. To cover up is to add shame to shame [28].”

BELC 04/15/2025. *We invited Pope Francis's BEG. You have been one of the most consistent popes. In your work, you have always vindicated the institution, bringing it closer to the community, especially to those who suffer the most needs. This hasn't happened for a long time. Agreed, Francis?* “I thank you, doctor, for those words that should have been acted upon to vindicate the deteriorated religious vision.” *If you agree, I would like to address some personal aspects.* “Yes, Doctor, go ahead.” *In elementary school, you had a conflict with your teacher, Lia. This led to a maternal reprimand at home that, in my opinion, was excessive, which you leave in ellipses, which speak louder than the description. This excessive maternal repression marked your relationship with her; your mother, right, Francis?* “True, doctor, it was something surprising even for myself, but that's how it happened.” *Fortunately, you met Esther, an interesting chemistry teacher and very genuine and committed social activist. Right, Francis?* “Right, doctor.” *The most effective way to stop you from studying medicine was for your mother to suggest it. Agreed, Francis? He laughs and affirms:* “Yes, doctor, that's how it was.” *Your reproaches to her were indirect. 1. By making you a pastor. 2. When your mother unexpectedly kneels before her already consecrated son. And, 3. By adopting, as a maternal figure, the support of the congregation and what the institution represents. Was it like that, Francis?* “Yes, doctor, that's how it was.” *And regarding the prevalence of sexual abuse in the Apostolic See, what do you say?* “Very regrettable and difficult to eliminate. In addition to the actions I've taken, much

remains to be done.” *Congratulations on your consistency, Francis.* “Thank you, doctor.” *What do you say about the BEL research?* “I'm intuiting, doctor, and I find it very interesting, and indeed it fulfills the purpose it is intended to serve. The BEG as such hasn't been considered, and it's very timely and necessary to position it this way, since it clears out the prevailing ideas, and best of all, it has no limits. And well, the NMEGO is what sets the limits. This much I can tell you for now.” *Would you like to add anything else?* “There's a pleasant atmosphere, very vectorized and calm.” *Of all the biospecies...* “Yes, doctor.” *Be well, Francis, keep taking care of your lungs.* “Yes, doctor, we've done our part and I'm satisfied.”

Conclusion

1. This is how the relentless, stealthy, and hard-to-modify imprinting syndrome of child sexual abuse is integrated. It is important to acknowledge that the determination of truth and falsehood can sometimes be influenced by dominant societal groups, prioritizing subjective biases over research findings and consistent statistical data. Therefore, it is advisable to consider contrasting approaches and perspectives in the examination of these complex topics. The harmful concealment of the deceptive sexual culture in the West made an industry is evident.
2. Whatever the reasons for continuing to hide and deny the pandemic of child sexual abuse and its grave consequences, allowing them to continue growing along with their devastating effects, they constitute contempt for children and a lack of respect for humanity.
3. Therefore, raising banners and arguments in defense of humanity and the new generations must be rejected as false and misleading, seeking only to continue pushing humanity toward a cataclysm with very serious and unstoppable consequences [29]. The worst calamity is the dictators of various countries who seek to impose their agenda on humanity.
4. Sexual hormones, uncontrolled by sexual abuse, distort their function and in this way will continue to affect humanity.
5. Humanity is irreparably poisoned by child sexual abuse and its consequences [Ints 03/18/2025].

Acknowledgment

I acknowledge Ruth A. López-Téllez for her clever assistance and permanent help.

Conflicts of Interest

None.

References

1. Bailey JM, Vasey P, Diamond L, Breedlove SM, Vilain E, et al. (2016) Sexual Orientation, Controversy, and Science. *Psychol Sci* 17: 45-101.
2. Bramblett JR, Darling CA (1997) Sexual contacts: Experiences, thoughts, and fantasies of adult male survivors of child sexual abuse. *J Sex Marital Ther* 23: 305-316.
3. Harper & Row (1972) *What Causes Homosexuality?* Harper & Row, USA.
4. Smith A (2004) Boarding school abuses, human rights, and reparations. *Soc Justice* 31: 89-102.
5. Martyniuk H (2014) *Understanding Rape in Prison.* US National Criminal Justice Reference Service, USA.

6. Rantala MJ, Marcinkowska UM (2011) The role of sexual imprinting and the Westermarck effect in mate choice in humans. *Behav Ecol Sociobiol* 65: 859-873.
7. Johnson CF (2004) Child sexual abuse. *The Lancet* 364: 462-470.
8. Baron M (1993) Genetic linkage and male homosexual orientation. *BMJ* 307: 337-338.
9. Joseph R (1999) Environmental Influences on Neural Plasticity, the Limbic System, Emotional Development and Attachment: A Review. *Child Psychiatry Hum Dev* 29: 189-208.
10. Braun K (2011) The Prefrontal-Limbic System: Development, Neuroanatomy, Function, and Implications for Socioemotional Development. *Clin Perinatol* 38: 685-702.
11. Bayer R (1987) *Homosexuality and American Psychiatry: The Politics of Diagnosis*. Princeton University Press, USA.
12. Wood B, Bartkowski JP (2004) Attribution Style and Public Policy Attitudes Toward Gay Rights. *Soc Sci Q* 85: 58-74.
13. Mongia M, Gupta AK, Vijay A, Sadhu R (2019) Management of stuttering using cognitive behavior therapy and mindfulness meditation. *Ind Psychiatry J* 28: 4-12.
14. Bernard RFL, Norbury CF (2023) Factors Associated with Symptoms of Anxiety and Depression in Children Who Stutter. *Lang Speech Hear Serv Sch* 54: 535-549.
15. Pereda N, Guilera G, Forns M, Gómez-Benito J (2009) The prevalence of child sexual abuse in community and student samples: A meta-analysis. *Clin Psychol Rev* 29: 328-338.
16. Maguire GA, Nguyen DL, Simonson KC, Kurz TL (2020) The pharmacologic treatment of stuttering and its neuropharmacologic basis. *Front Neurosci (online)* 14: 1-8.
17. Walden TA, Frankel CB, Buhr AP, Johnson KN, Conture EG, et al. (2012) Dual Diathesis-Stressor Model of Emotional and Linguistic Contributions to Developmental Stuttering. *J Abnorm Child Psychol* 40: 633-644.
18. Nippold MA, Packman A (2012) Managing Stuttering Beyond the Pre-school Years. *Lang Speech Hear Serv Sch Research Forum* 43: 338-343.
19. Loomes R, Hull L, Mandy WPL (2017) What is the male-to-female ratio in autism spectrum disorder? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry* 56: 466-474.
20. Ku J, Koo C (2021) Tics of Trauma: Unique Case of Trauma-Associated Psychogenic Tics in an Adolescent Patient. *Cureus* 13: 17652.
21. Comings DE, Comings BG (1993) Sexual Abuse or Tourette Syndrome? *Social Work* 38: 347-350.
22. Cuevas-Sosa A (2023) The biocreativity of intuitions, young planets with humans; imprinting, homosexuality, sexual abuse, stuttering and autism. *Int J Complement Alt Med* 16: 98-110.
23. Cuevas Sosa A (1999) *Paidofilia y efebofilia en sacerdotes y monjas*. Ciudad de México, México.
24. Saer JJ, Entenado El, Rica C (2016) *Ediciones Lanzallamas*.
25. Tello-Díaz C (2024) *Sexual recession*. Milenio newspaper, México.
26. Dyvik EH (2024) *Number of nuclear warheads worldwide*.
27. Caroline D (2025) *Y dejé de llamarte papá*. Prólogo. Editorial Planeta, Barcelona, España, México.
28. Francisco P, Esperanza (2025) *La Autobiografía*. Plaza y Janés México, México.
29. Cuevas-Sosa A (2023) Actualization. Sexual abuse, imprinting, and Tourette's syndrome. Protagonist, deuteragonist, tritagonist, and hybris. *Int J Complement Alt Med* 16: 182-188.

- Advances In Industrial Biotechnology | ISSN: 2639-5665
- Advances In Microbiology Research | ISSN: 2689-694X
- Archives Of Surgery And Surgical Education | ISSN: 2689-3126
- Archives Of Urology
- Archives Of Zoological Studies | ISSN: 2640-7779
- Current Trends Medical And Biological Engineering
- International Journal Of Case Reports And Therapeutic Studies | ISSN: 2689-310X
- Journal Of Addiction & Addictive Disorders | ISSN: 2578-7276
- Journal Of Agronomy & Agricultural Science | ISSN: 2689-8292
- Journal Of AIDS Clinical Research & STDs | ISSN: 2572-7370
- Journal Of Alcoholism Drug Abuse & Substance Dependence | ISSN: 2572-9594
- Journal Of Allergy Disorders & Therapy | ISSN: 2470-749X
- Journal Of Alternative Complementary & Integrative Medicine | ISSN: 2470-7562
- Journal Of Alzheimers & Neurodegenerative Diseases | ISSN: 2572-9608
- Journal Of Anesthesia & Clinical Care | ISSN: 2378-8879
- Journal Of Angiology & Vascular Surgery | ISSN: 2572-7397
- Journal Of Animal Research & Veterinary Science | ISSN: 2639-3751
- Journal Of Aquaculture & Fisheries | ISSN: 2576-5523
- Journal Of Atmospheric & Earth Sciences | ISSN: 2689-8780
- Journal Of Biotech Research & Biochemistry
- Journal Of Brain & Neuroscience Research
- Journal Of Cancer Biology & Treatment | ISSN: 2470-7546
- Journal Of Cardiology Study & Research | ISSN: 2640-768X
- Journal Of Cell Biology & Cell Metabolism | ISSN: 2381-1943
- Journal Of Clinical Dermatology & Therapy | ISSN: 2378-8771
- Journal Of Clinical Immunology & Immunotherapy | ISSN: 2378-8844
- Journal Of Clinical Studies & Medical Case Reports | ISSN: 2378-8801
- Journal Of Community Medicine & Public Health Care | ISSN: 2381-1978
- Journal Of Cytology & Tissue Biology | ISSN: 2378-9107
- Journal Of Dairy Research & Technology | ISSN: 2688-9315
- Journal Of Dentistry Oral Health & Cosmesis | ISSN: 2473-6783
- Journal Of Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders | ISSN: 2381-201X
- Journal Of Emergency Medicine Trauma & Surgical Care | ISSN: 2378-8798
- Journal Of Environmental Science Current Research | ISSN: 2643-5020
- Journal Of Food Science & Nutrition | ISSN: 2470-1076
- Journal Of Forensic Legal & Investigative Sciences | ISSN: 2473-733X
- Journal Of Gastroenterology & Hepatology Research | ISSN: 2574-2566
- Journal Of Genetics & Genomic Sciences | ISSN: 2574-2485
- Journal Of Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine | ISSN: 2381-8662
- Journal Of Hematology Blood Transfusion & Disorders | ISSN: 2572-2999
- Journal Of Hospice & Palliative Medical Care
- Journal Of Human Endocrinology | ISSN: 2572-9640
- Journal Of Infectious & Non Infectious Diseases | ISSN: 2381-8654
- Journal Of Internal Medicine & Primary Healthcare | ISSN: 2574-2493
- Journal Of Light & Laser Current Trends
- Journal Of Medicine Study & Research | ISSN: 2639-5657
- Journal Of Modern Chemical Sciences
- Journal Of Nanotechnology Nanomedicine & Nanobiotechnology | ISSN: 2381-2044
- Journal Of Neonatology & Clinical Pediatrics | ISSN: 2378-878X
- Journal Of Nephrology & Renal Therapy | ISSN: 2473-7313
- Journal Of Non Invasive Vascular Investigation | ISSN: 2572-7400
- Journal Of Nuclear Medicine Radiology & Radiation Therapy | ISSN: 2572-7419
- Journal Of Obesity & Weight Loss | ISSN: 2473-7372
- Journal Of Ophthalmology & Clinical Research | ISSN: 2378-8887
- Journal Of Orthopedic Research & Physiotherapy | ISSN: 2381-2052
- Journal Of Otolaryngology Head & Neck Surgery | ISSN: 2573-010X
- Journal Of Pathology Clinical & Medical Research
- Journal Of Pharmacology Pharmaceutics & Pharmacovigilance | ISSN: 2639-5649
- Journal Of Physical Medicine Rehabilitation & Disabilities | ISSN: 2381-8670
- Journal Of Plant Science Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3743
- Journal Of Practical & Professional Nursing | ISSN: 2639-5681
- Journal Of Protein Research & Bioinformatics
- Journal Of Psychiatry Depression & Anxiety | ISSN: 2573-0150
- Journal Of Pulmonary Medicine & Respiratory Research | ISSN: 2573-0177
- Journal Of Reproductive Medicine Gynaecology & Obstetrics | ISSN: 2574-2574
- Journal Of Stem Cells Research Development & Therapy | ISSN: 2381-2060
- Journal Of Surgery Current Trends & Innovations | ISSN: 2578-7284
- Journal Of Toxicology Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3735
- Journal Of Translational Science And Research
- Journal Of Vaccines Research & Vaccination | ISSN: 2573-0193
- Journal Of Virology & Antivirals
- Sports Medicine And Injury Care Journal | ISSN: 2689-8829
- Trends In Anatomy & Physiology | ISSN: 2640-7752

Submit Your Manuscript: <https://www.heraldopenaccess.us/submit-manuscript>